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INVESTIGATION PARAMETERS REQUIRED FOR THE PERFORMANCE OF IC ENGINE

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ABSTRACT

Developing countries like India mainly depend on other fuel supplying countries due to which the economics of country is moderate. Due to industrialization and urbanization usage of fuel for transportation has been sharply increased. Many research scholars are working for alternative fuels to substitute the petroleum. The present study gives as over view the parameters considered for the investigation of I C Engines. Combustion parameters, performance parameters, emission parameters have been explained in details.

KEYWORDS: Alternative fuels, Combustion parameters, performance parameters, emission parameters.